

Synthesis of dye based colored polyesters by interfacial polymerization

Lakshmikanta^{a*} and Bimal Verma^b

^aDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Sri Shankaracharya College of Engineering & Technology, Bhilai, Durg-490 020, Chhattisgarh, India

^bDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra-825 215, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : kanta_27lakshmi@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-788-2291606

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Abstract : This article describes the synthesis of phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes by condensation reaction of aliphatic dicarboxylic acid like – adipic acid with four different aromatic hydroxyl compounds like – phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and β -naphthol separately. The synthesized dyes were then used for synthesis of polyesters by stirred interfacial polycondensation technique with terephthaloyl chloride (TPHC) in 1,2-dichloroethane. These colored polyesters contains an aliphatic lactone ring. An oxygen-bridge exists in the case of fluorescein type of dyes. The structures of dyes were confirmed by elemental analysis, solubility test, FTIR and thermal behavior by DSC. All the four polyesters were characterized by elemental analysis, solubility test and FTIR.

Keywords : Phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes, interfacial polycondensation, terephthaloyl chloride, aliphatic lactone ring.

Introduction

Colorants are generally added to many commercially important organic polymers to achieve the desired artistic and decorative effects. Under operating condition monomeric dyes generally undergo sublimation or leaching and the presence of dust also causes problem. Literature survey reveals that due to toxicity¹ of colored plastics by monomeric dyes, it is avoided in food packaging. A very few dyes and aluminium hydrate lakes are used in food items and few pigments in drug and cosmetics. Tethering of these dyes in polymers has solved these problems and new class of materials – colored polymers/polymeric colorants, have gained recognition and applicability as alternative method of coloration due to presence of chromophoric system forming part in their structures. Colored polymer/polymeric colorant do not sublime, are non-abrasive, and generally have low toxicity. Many examples are found in chemical literature which summarizes the area²⁻⁶ that combination of polymer chemistry and color chemistry is virtually inexhaustible. Polymeric colorants/colored polymers are applied in a wide variety of technologies. Their applications are dependent on their higher molar mass. The colored polymers, e.g. polymeric dyes

are useful polymers or oligomers due to their high tinctorial strength^{7,8}. The polymeric dyes are used for dyeing and printing of textile materials, which shows better fastness to crocking and to solvents than pigment-dyed or pigment-printed fabrics⁹. The polymeric dyes are also used as paper colorants, fugitive stains for registration purpose, printing, plastic coloration, photoconductive polymers, photographic and reprographic application, immunoassay procedures, process-efficiency monitoring, fluorescent brighteners, electro-conductive polymers, photocell assemblies, colored photo-resists and liquid-crystalline polymeric dye systems. The literature survey reveals that many researchers¹⁰⁻¹⁸ have reported the use of dyes, especially phenolphthalein and fluorescein in polymer synthesis. Thermotropic liquid-crystalline random copolyesters, thermotropic liquid-crystalline polyphosphate esters, optically active poly (ester-imide)s, cardopolysulfonates, polycynurates, are also reported¹⁹⁻²³ by using phenolphthalein. The use of phenolphthalein and fluorescein, in polymer synthesis especially by Interfacial Polycondensation Technique have been reported by previous workers^{12,16,17,24-26}. The phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes having aliphatic lactone ring,

synthesized from condensation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids with various aromatic diols and their derivatives is reported by previous workers²⁷. These dyes also act as indicators in place of phenolphthalein and fluorescein in the same pH-range. But no work has been found in the synthesis of colored polymers from these phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes having aliphatic lactone ring by using interfacial polycondensation technique.

In this article we describe, the synthesis of colored polyester from phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dye moieties by the help of Interfacial Polycondensation Technique, which is highly effective procedure for the rapid preparation of many polymers in high molecular weight, and in an easily isolated form as compared to other technique, economic consideration, safety and environmental factors. This method of polymer synthesis has been adopted with the goal of introducing a series of products into the existing facilities. To achieve this objective, four different phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes (two each) have been synthesized from condensation of four different aromatic hydroxyl compounds like – phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and β -naphthol separately with adipic acid. The synthesized dyes which are acting as aromatic diols in turn, interfacially polycondensed

with terephthaloyl chloride (TPHC) in 1,2-dichloroethane, to synthesize four different colored polyesters.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of dyes :

Depending upon the basic structure, the dyes were categorized into two types : (i) phenolphthalein type of dyes, which were synthesized from either phenol or β -naphthol (D-2A and D-2D), (ii) fluorescein type of dyes, which were synthesized from either resorcinol or pyrogallol (D-2B and D-2C). Since, the structures of these types of dyes are already established²⁷⁻²⁹, so here, the elemental analysis, solubility test, FT-IR, and DSC of the dyes have been discussed.

Elemental analysis :

All the synthesized dyes were dark colored, amorphous powder (Table 1) and their yields were in the range 50–60%. The dyes synthesized from resorcinol have shown higher yield as compared to others. The elemental analysis of dyes (Table 2) agreed well with the theoretical value of the chemical structure.

Solubility test :

All the dyes prepared by condensation reaction with the loss of water molecules, were soluble in NaOH and

Table 1. Data on reactants used, reaction time, colour and colour change in alkaline and acidic medium of dyes

Dye code	Aromatic diols (g)	Aliphatic dicarboxylic acid (g)	Reaction time (h)	Colour	Colour in dil. NaOH	Colour in dil. HCl
D-2A	Phenol (9.4)	Adipic acid	8–10	Black	Bright brown	Dull brown
D-2B	Resorcinol (11.0)	acid	6–7	Black	Fluorescent pink	Orange
D-2C	Pyrogallol (12.6)	(7.3)	8–9	Shiny black	Bright brown	Light brown
D-2D	β -Naphthol (14.4)		8–9	Dark brown	Yellowish green	Black

Table 2. Data on yield, molecular formula, molecular weight and elemental analysis of individual dyes

Dye code	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Elemental analysis (%) : Calcd. (Expt.)	
				Carbon	Hydrogen
D-2A	54	$C_{18}H_{18}O_4$	298.144	72.45 (72.35)	6.08 (6.12)
D-2B	60	$C_{18}H_{16}O_5$	312.128	69.20 (69.15)	5.17 (5.22)
D-2C	50	$C_{18}H_{16}O_7$	344.128	62.77 (62.81)	4.69 (4.58)
D-2D	51	$C_{26}H_{22}O_4$	398.176	78.36 (78.28)	5.57 (5.61)

hot alcohol. All these dyes showed color change in acidic and alkaline media (Table 1) almost in the same pH-range, like – phenolphthalein and fluorescein.

FT-IR analysis :

All the four dyes (Fig. 1) have shown following characteristic absorption bands²⁷⁻²⁹ (cm^{-1}) : Ar.O-H (str.) 3312, 3200, 3251, 3284; Ar=C-H (str.) 3124–3057; C=C ring (str.) 1639–1456; methylene C-H (str.) 2950 ± 15 (asym), 2830 ± 20 (sym); lactone (C=O str.) 1708–1695; (C-O str.) 1263–1218; (O-H in-plane bending) 1436–1392; (O-H out-of-plane bending) 769–626; (=C-H

out-of-plane bending) 854–788. In addition to all these bands, dye D-2B and D-2C have shown aromatic etheral C-O stretching band near $1250\text{--}1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$. All these dyes have also shown absorption around $725 \pm 4\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is due to the characteristic $-(\text{CH}_2)_n$ -skeletal vibration, where $n \geq 4$ for aliphatic group of lactone ring. All these support the structure of dye.

Thermal characterization :

The thermal behaviour of dyes was supported by : (a) DSC thermogram (Fig. 2) in N_2 atmosphere and (b) action of heat on dyes under normal condition (Table 3) by simply heating the sample in a crucible. The dyes did not

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of dyes → D-2A, D-2B, D-2C, D-2D and terephthaloyl chloride (TPHC).

Fig. 2. DSC thermogram of dyes → D-2A, D-2B, D-2C and D-2D.

Table 3. Data on the thermal analysis of dyes

Dye code	Action of heat in presence of O ₂ Melting/sticking temp. (°C)	DSC in N ₂ atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min	
		Entrapped/absorbed H ₂ O [temp. (°C)]	Melting*/decomp. temp. (°C)
D-2A	230	64.93	242.5*
D-2B	210–260	76.25	289.76
D-2C	235	67.85	339.59*
D-2D	300	75.89	297.02

show any melting, except D-2B, which showed broad range melting from 210–260 °C. The dyes D-2A and D-2C started to stick to the surface of crucible after 220 °C for at least 5–6 °C and after that started to char with fumes. The D-2D neither showed melting nor sticking but it simply charred.

From the DSC thermograms, it was found that, either one or two endothermic peaks were present in all the thermograms. The endothermic peak within 100 °C was due to absorbed or entrapped water molecule in the dyes. In most of the cases, after this endothermic peak – the nature of thermogram moved parallel to the baseline to a certain temperature and after that, it deviated in upward direction. This indicated the onset of decomposition of dyes after that particular temperature. The second endothermic peak had observed in the thermogram of D-2A and D-2C which was due to melting of these dyes (marked by asterisks in Table 4) and reflected the crystalline nature of these dyes, although no sharp melting was observed during the action of heat. A broad range sharp melting was observed for D-2B during action of heat, which existed from 210–260 °C and after 260 °C the movement of melt was ceased, but it has not showed any endothermic peak around this temperature range in the thermogram. The deviation of thermogram from baseline took place around 290 °C and indicated its decomposition. These values of thermal analysis²⁹, more or less agrees well with the reported²⁷ melting/sticking/decom-

position temperature (i.e. ≥ 250 °C) in all the cases.

Synthesis and characterization of polymers :

All the polymers were synthesized by interfacial polycondensation of dyes (having two -OH groups) with terephthaloyl chloride, each dissolved in polar and non-polar solvents respectively. The synthetic method was based on the Schotten-Baumann reaction. All the four polymers were granular, dark colored powder with the yield in the range 59–82% (Table 5). The fluorescein type of dyes showed higher yield of polymers as compared to phenolphthalein type of dyes. Among four polymers, the polymer P-2B, having resorcinol moiety showed bright color (Table 4). The polymers were characterized by elemental analysis, solubility test, and FT-IR.

Elemental analysis :

The elemental analysis of characteristic repeating unit of polymers agreed well with the theoretical value (Table 5). A slight deviation may be due to incomplete combustion of polymers in furnace.

Solubility test :

All the four polymers were sparingly soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in toluene, chloroform, tetrahydrofuran (THF), and cresol. All the polymers were soluble at room temperature in polar aprotic solvents like – dimethyl formamide (except P-2B), and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). The P-2B was soluble in DMSO at 120 °C but below the boiling point of DMSO

Table 4. Data on reactants used, color and stirring time of polymers

Polymer code	Dye (g)	Terephthaloyl chloride (g)	1,2-Dichloroethane (ml)	NaOH (g)	<i>n</i> -Heptane (ml)	Color	Stirring time (min)
P-2A	D-2A (2.98)	2.4	40	1.0	50	Brown	40
P-2B	D-2B (3.12)	2.1	40	1.5		Brick red	25
P-2C	D-2C (3.44)	2.1	40	1.0		Dirty black	45
P-2D	D-2D (3.98)	2.9	60	2.0		Yellowish brown	15

Table 5. Data on yield, molecular formula, molecular weight and elemental analysis of repeating unit of polymer

Polymer code	Yield (%)	Mol. formula of repeating unit	Mol. wt. of repeating unit	Elemental analysis (%) : Calcd. (Expt.)	
				Carbon	Hydrogen
P-2A	63.8	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₆	428	72.89 (72.39)	4.67 (4.49)
P-2B	71.2	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₇	442	70.58 (70.16)	4.07 (3.89)
P-2C	82	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	474	65.82 (65.68)	3.79 (3.59)
P-2D	59.2	C ₃₄ H ₂₄ O ₆	528	77.27 (77.09)	4.54 (4.28)

(i.e. 180 °C). The good solubility of these polymers in polar aprotic solvents may be attributed due to the introduction of ester linkage in the main chain as well as the presence of lactone ring¹⁷, which increases the polarity³⁰ along the polymer chain. The low solubility of P-2B in DMSO was due to close packing of polymer chain^{28,29,31}.

FT-IR analysis :

The FTIR spectra of polymers have been shown in Fig. 3. It showed all the absorbance shown by their corresponding dyes from which they were synthesized except, the aromatic O-H stretching band. The absence of (Ar.O-H) stretching showed the complete esterification of dyes except, the dye (D-2C) synthesized from pyrogallol moiety (Ar.O-H str.) near 3400 cm⁻¹. This indicated that, like other dyes (synthesized from phenol, resorcinol, and β-naphthol), in this dye too, the phenolic group para to the central C-atom joining the two benzene/naphthalene ring involved in esterification because, formation of quinonoid structure^{17,28,29} takes place by this -OH group only and another -OH group remains free. All the polymers showed strong absorbance near 1750–1720 cm⁻¹ for (C=O) stretching of ester as well as lactone ring^{17,22,25,26,32–34}. The strong absorbance near 1340–1200 cm⁻¹ of (C–O) stretching vibration further supported the presence of ester group as well as lactone ring in polymer structure^{22,29,35}. The (O–C=C) asymmetric stretching near 1168–1130 cm⁻¹ were indicative of aryl conjugated system^{33,34}.

Experimental

Materials :

Adipic acid, phenol, hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, 1,2-dichloroethane (S.d. fine chem. Ltd.), resorcinol

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of polymers → P-2A, P-2B, P-2C and P-2D.

(Merck), pyrogallol, *n*-heptane (CDH), β -naphthol (Ranbaxy), terephthaloyl chloride (ACROS), dimethyl sulfoxide (RANKEM), sodium hydroxide (NICE). All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and used as received except 1,2-dichloroethane and *n*-heptane, these were distilled before use.

Synthesis of dyes :

The methodology for synthesis of dyes is based on the reported procedure²⁷⁻²⁹. All the four dyes have been synthesized by condensation reaction of aliphatic dicarboxylic acid like - adipic acid with four different aromatic diols, like - phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and β -naphthol separately. The aromatic diols (2 mole) and adipic acid (1 mole) were taken in a 500 ml round-bottomed flask fitted with air-condenser, and heated in presence of 5-6 drops conc. H_2SO_4 at 150-170 °C, in an oil bath for about 6-10 h, depending upon the nature of aromatic hydroxyl compound used, by means of heating mantle. On completion of reaction, a solidified mass of crude dye on cooling was purified by dissolving it in dilute NaOH and reprecipitated by dilute HCl, filtered, washed with distilled water 3-4 times followed by cold ethanol and dried for two hours at 70 °C. The quantity of various reagents taken for each dye is given in Table 1 along with reaction time. The synthesis of dyes is presented in Scheme 1.

Synthesis of polymers :

The dyes synthesized in Scheme 1, were polymerized by Stirred Interfacial Polycondensation Technique with terephthaloyl chloride (TPHC). The reported procedure^{28-30,36} for polymer synthesis is as follows :

In 250 ml of distilled water the required quantity of respective dyes and sodium hydroxide were dissolved. The filtered dye solution was then stirred with high speed in the jar of Warring Blender covered with heavy duty aluminum foil pierced at the center to introduce reagents. A solution of required quantity of terephthaloyl chloride was prepared in 40-60 ml of distilled 1,2-dichloroethane and poured into the dye solution as quickly as possible. The mixture was stirred for 15-45 min at 25-32 °C \pm 2 °C. The faded color of dye and increase in viscosity of the solution was the indicative of the progress of the reaction. 50 ml of distilled *n*-heptane was then added to remove some of the 1,2-dichloroethane and stirred slowly

Scheme 1. Synthetic scheme for dyes.

where, Ar-OH =

and Dye,

D-2A = Phenol-adipine

D-2B = Resorcinol-adipine

D-2C = Pyrogallol-adipine

D-2D = β -Naphthol-adipine

for 7-8 min, filtered, washed with distilled water 3-4 times and dried for 5-6 h at 70 °C. The details of each reactant used along with stirring time are given in Table 4 and synthetic route for polymer synthesis is shown in Scheme 2.

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Scheme 2. Synthetic scheme for polymers.

where, Polymer

P-2A = Poly(terephthaloyl-phenol-adipine)

P-2B = Poly(terephthaloyl-resorcinol-adipine)

P-2C = Poly(terephthaloyl-pyrogallol-adipine)

P-2D = Poly(terephthaloyl-β-naphthol-adipine)

Characterization :

The elemental analysis of dyes and polymers were carried out on Carlo ERBA-EA-1108 elemental analyzer. The solubility was checked qualitatively by taking a mustard grain of each dye/polymer and dissolved in 5 ml of different organic solvents/alkali. FT-IR of all the dyes, terephthaloyl chloride and polymers were recorded on Shimadzu-FTIR-8201 PC by incorporating the dyes and polymers in Diffused Reflection Spectroscopic (DRS) mode and the terephthaloyl chloride in KBr pellet. DSC of dyes were carried out on Mettler Toledo Model-DSC 821 (-60 to 500 °C) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in nitrogen atmosphere.

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